

Synergistic electrical and rheological effects in carbon nanotube/carbon black-epoxy three phase systems

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SUMMARY

Epoxy nanocomposites including carbon nanotubes (MWCNT) and carbon black (CB) were investigated by means of their electrical and rheological percolation behaviour. Due to synergistic dynamic effects in charge transport the inclusion of both MWCNT and CB in a multiphase epoxy system leads to the same electrical behaviour compared to the binary MWCNT-epoxy one. Structural analysis showed the formation of a co-supporting network of CB and MWCNT in the multiphase system. Thus, a significant amount of MWCNT can be replaced by CB without worsening the electrical behaviour in bulk epoxy nanocomposites.

Keywords: Nanocomposite, hybrid, epoxy, carbon nanotube, carbon black

INTRODUCTION

Carbon-based nanoparticles such as CB and MWCNT are suitable to impart electrical conductivity to polymers, leading to various applications where antistatic or conductive behaviours of polymers are required [1]. In principle, MWCNT provide better electrical properties compared to CB [2,3]. By using more than one type of nanoparticle, multiphase systems can be produced. Depending on the combination of different types of fillers, synergistic effects can be observed, mostly studied in terms of electrical percolation. For example, the addition of layered silica to carbon nanotube epoxy leads to a decrease in the percolation threshold [4]. Similar results were found in previous studies for carbon nanofibre/layered silica epoxy composites [5]. Increasing electrical conductivities were also found in epoxy nanocomposites including carbon black and fumed silica [6] or MWCNT and graphite nanoplatelets [7]. In contrast, earlier works of our group report decreasing electrical conductivities if titania nanoparticles are added to MWCNT epoxy systems [8].

In this work, we combine MWCNT and CB in order to obtain a multiphase structure. When blending such kind of two conductive fillers in an epoxy matrix, it is likely that co-supporting networks of both fillers form out. This can lead to improved electrical conductivity of the polymer [7,9]. In addition to that, Sun et al. found synergistic effects for mixed CB/MWCNT filled polypropylene [10].

MATERIALS

The epoxy polymer is based on a DGEBA resin (LY556), cured with an anhydride hardener (CH917) and an imidazole accelerator (DY070). This epoxy system is commercially available and certified for aeronautic and space applications. The system provides good mechanical and chemical properties. Additionally, it provides a good processability with a mixing viscosity of about 800 mPas. The system is provided by Huntsman[®], Switzerland.

The multi-wall carbon nanotubes (MWCNT) are provided by Arkema[®], France. They exhibit a mean outer diameter of about 15 nm with length of about 10 μm . The specific surface area is about 250 m^2/g . They are commercially available under the trade name Graphistrength C100[®]. The carbon black (CB Printex XE2[®]) is provided by Evonik-Degussa[®], Germany. The mean primary particle size is of about 30 nm. In dispersed systems CB appears as aggregates of primary particles with length of up to few hundred nanometers.

EXPERIMENTAL

The epoxy nanocomposites were produced using a high shear mixing process including a three-roll-mill (Exakt 120E). First, the nanoparticles were manually stirred in the resin (LY556). Afterwards, the pre-dispersed suspension was given batchwise onto the rolls with dwell times of about two minutes. The final dispersion takes place between the rolls of the three-roll-mill. The small gap between the rolls of 5 μm leads to very high shear forces (up to 200,000 s^{-1}) throughout the whole volume which cause a superior state of dispersion of the nanoparticles. Details about this dispersion technique can be found in earlier publications by our group [11,12]. After dispersion of the nanoparticles in the resin, hardener and accelerator were added in a vacuum dissolver as described in [13]. The filler concentration was varied in small steps from very low (0.0025 wt.%) to high (0.6 wt.%) weight content. In the ternary systems, the ratio between CB and MWCNT were set to 1:1, e.g., 0.2 wt.% CB plus 0.2 wt.% MWCNT.

The uncured samples were poured into an aluminium mould (100 x 180 mm^2) and cured in an oven following the curing cycle recommended by Huntsman (4h at 80°C plus 8h at 140°C). After curing, samples for impedance spectroscopy were machined from the middle part of the sample. For each filler content four samples were cut to a geometry of 10x10x1 mm^3 . The surfaces were covered with conductive silver paint. In order to obtain information about the dispersion in the cured state, the AC electrical conductivity was measured in the frequency range between 20 Hz and 1 MHz with a HP4826 impedance analyzer. The electrical conductivity values used in the percolation diagram were taken at 1 kHz. Transmission electron micrographs were taken using a Philips EM 400 at 120 kV. Ultra thin films of the nanocomposites ($w= 50 \text{ nm}$) were obtained by ultramicrotome cutting. Transmission light micrographs were taken using a standard light microscope. Samples were prepared from conductivity samples by grinding down to 0.2 mm with additional polishing. Rheological tests were performed prior to curing in a TA ARES[®] rheometer in oscillatory mode under strain controlled conditions. The suspension was directly given to the rheometer after dispersion in the three-roll-mill.

RESULTS

Structural analysis

Transmission electron and light microscopy were performed on samples with a filler concentration of 0.1 wt.%. In case of the ternary CB/MWCNT system, a dispersion of CB and MWCNT on the primary particle level can be found, leading to co-supporting networks, which were also found for other combinations of carbon based particles [7,10]. This good intermixing of both types of particles avoids the formation of domains or other substructures as reported for other nanoparticle combinations [6,14].

Figure 1: Co-supporting networks hybrid structure of the three-phase nanocomposites (CB/MWCNT/epoxy).

The co-supporting networks of CB and MWCNT can also be found at lower magnifications in transmission light microscopy revealing differences in the spatial distribution of nanoparticle agglomerates and their different formation of networks. In Figure 2 images of nanocomposites containing 0.1 wt.% are shown. The binary MWCNT as well as the ternary CB/MWCNT systems show a formation of dense networks which lead to conductivities above the percolation threshold. Although the ternary system contains of 0.05 wt.% of each of the nanoparticles (0.1 wt.% in total), the network structure appears almost as dense as the binary MWCNT system. The CB system does not show a comparable network structure, thus leading to conductivities below its specific percolation threshold.

Figure 2: TLM-image of nanocomposites containing 0.1 wt.% of nanoparticles showing the spatial distribution of agglomerates and their network formation [2]

Electrical conductivity

The structural features of the different nanocomposite systems are reflected in the electrical percolation behaviour (see Figure 3). The binary CB-epoxy system exhibits the lowest conductivity and the highest percolation threshold (0.085 wt.) of all three systems. The binary MWCNT-epoxy system poses a percolation threshold of 0.025 wt.%, three times lower than the CB-system. The conductivity at high filler concentrations is up to two orders of magnitude higher since the number of tunnelling resistances is much lower for high aspect ratio fillers as the used MWCNT. Interestingly, the percolation threshold as well the overall conductivity is almost the identical for the ternary CB/MWCNT-epoxy and the binary MWCNT-epoxy, although 50% of the MWCNT is replaced by CB which poses a much lower aspect ratio. The dashed line represents the sum curve of both binary CB-epoxy and MWCNT-epoxy conductivity which leads to the conclusion that synergistic effects must have taken place in the network formation or occur during charge transport in the cured nanocomposites.

Figure 3: Percolation curve for the CB and MWCNT nanocomposites, right: hybrid structure of the three-phase nanocomposites (CB/MWCNT/epoxy) [2].

Case 1 assumes CB changing the MWCNT network structure. It is known that MWCNT form a fractal structure which is multiple redundant, featuring branches in the network which do not contribute to the conductive pathway, so called “dead” branches. Considering now CB aggregates shortcutting some of these “dead” MWCNT branches new conductive pathways are formed. Additionally, the tunnelling distance and the number of tunnelling contacts determine the overall conductivity [15,16]. Following this argumentation, CB preferable shortcut parts of the MWCNT network rather than to build up an own network in CB/MWCNT ternary composites.

Since we found co-supporting CB/MWCNT networks in ternary systems, it is more likely that CB is also incorporated in conductive pathways. In principle, if a MWCNT is substituted by several spherical CB particles or CB aggregates increasing resistance over a certain length should be found which results in a significantly lower overall conductivity. The reason why the experimental results and the sum curve in Figure 1 differ significantly may be explained by the fact that CB aggregates preferably shortcut small distances of two neighbouring contact resistance points. It is obvious that the distance between two contact points in a MWCNT network is not constant and can be much shorter than an actual nanotube length. Another reason may be due to the production process leading to highly entangled and curved MWCNT. Thus, it can be assumed that the statistic length of a MWCNT-MWCNT contact is in the length scale of a CB aggregate (few hundred nanometers).

Mechanisms in ternary CB/MWCNT composites

Figure 4: Principles of conductive pathway formation in ternary CB/MWCNT systems [2].

Rheological analysis

Figure 5 shows the storage shear modulus at low frequency (0.5 Hz) of the nanocomposite suspensions as a function of the filler content. All of the three nanoparticle systems show an increase in the storage shear modulus at a critical filler content, the so called rheological percolation threshold. For the binary MWCNT system this percolation threshold is the lowest of all three systems. The binary CB system exhibits the highest percolation threshold, around three times higher than the binary MWCNT system. This difference in rheological percolation threshold corresponds well with the electrical percolation threshold. Nevertheless, the rheological percolation threshold is around one order of magnitude higher than the electrical percolation threshold for a specific nanoparticle-epoxy [17]. This is mainly attributed to prevalent reagglomeration effects during curing. According to the findings in electrical percolation behaviour, the ternary CB/MWCNT system shows a behaviour similar to the binary MWCNT system. Again, the difference between the binary CB system and the dashed line (computed sum storage shear moduli of the binary CB and MWCNT systems) in Figure 5 shows the presence of a synergistic structure. In this case, the structure is formed directly after dispersion and before curing leading to the conclusion that the synergistic effects are mainly based on a co-supporting network structure rather than in changes in the reagglomeration dynamics.

Figure 5: Rheological percolation graph of the uncured nanocomposite suspensions (CB/MWCNT/epoxy) [17].

CONCLUSIONS

The potential of CB and MWCNT as conductive fillers in an epoxy polymer was studied by investigating the electrical and rheological percolation behaviours. MWCNT exhibit a higher potential as a functional filler compared to CB due to their higher aspect ratio, resulting in a decreased electrical percolation threshold and higher bulk conductivity for high filler contents. As a drawback, the viscosity of the MWCNT systems increases at lower filler contents as in the CB systems, which may lead to problems in processing. Additionally, ternary systems including CB and MWCNT were produced featuring a co-supporting network structure which is reflected in the electrical behaviour. The electrical percolation threshold as well as the conductivity is preserved when half of the amount of MWCNT is substituted by CB. Since the conductivities at high filler contents of the ternary CB/MWCNT-epoxy and the binary MWCNT-epoxy are similar, it is likely that MWCNT dominate the formation of the network structure in ternary CB/MWCNT-epoxy. Besides that, CB might shortcut some parts of the MWCNT network branches or substitutes some MWCNT contacts.

This work showed that a combination of conductive particles lead to preserved electrical properties with a simultaneous significant reduction of the MWCNT amount. Thus, MWCNT can be substituted by a considerable amount of another type of conductive nanoparticle if the intermixing is sufficiently high and if this second type of nanoparticles possesses similar reagglomeration tendencies. The variation of the CB to MWCNT ratio may lead to even more improved electrical properties by adjusting an optimum microstructure.

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